

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of azetidin-2-one containing pyrazoline derivatives

Shailesh H. Shah^{a*} and Pankaj S. Patel^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Patel J.B.R. Arts, Patel A.M.R. Commerce & Patel J.D.K.D. Science College, Borsad-388 540, Gujarat, India

E-mail : shailchem@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sheth L.H. Science College, Mansa, Gujarat, India

Manuscript received online 25 July 2012, revised 26 July 2012, accepted 31 July 2012

Abstract : Pyrazolines are well-known and important nitrogen containing 5-membered heterocyclic compounds and various methods have been worked out for their synthesis. A new series of 3-chloro-1-{4-[5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-pyrazol-3-yl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one are synthesized by reacting 3-chloro-1-{4-[3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one with 99% hydrazine hydrate. All these compounds were characterized by means of their IR, ¹H NMR, spectroscopic data and microanalysis. All the synthesized products were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity. All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities by broth dilution method.

Keywords : Chalcones, 2-pyrazolines, azetidin-2-one, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Pyrazol belongs to the family of azoles, five member heterocyclic. Pyrazolines have proved to be the most useful framework for biological activities. Pyrazolines have attracted attention of medicinal chemists for both with regard to heterocyclic chemistry and the pharmacological activities associated with them. The pharmaceutical importance of these compounds lies in the fact that they can be effectively utilized as anticancer¹, insecticidal², antibacterial³, antifungal⁴, antidepressant⁵⁻⁸, anticonvulsant^{9,10}, anti-inflammatory¹¹, antibacterial¹² and antitumor¹³ properties. Moreover, many selectively fluoro-substituted organic compounds show peculiar pharmacological and agrochemical properties¹⁴⁻¹⁷. As evident from the literature, in recent years a significant portion of research work in heterocyclic chemistry has been devoted to pyrazolines containing different aryl groups as substituents.

In the present study we report the reaction of 3-chloro-1-{4-[3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one with 99% hydrazine hydrate to form pyrazoline (**4a-j**). The structures of the various

synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR spectral data and elemental analysis (Table 1). These compounds were also screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

The IR spectra were recorded on IR affinity-1, DRS-8000A, Shimadzu, Ptc. Ltd., Japan spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR was recorded in DMSO on Bruker Advance II 400 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC-using silica gel-G (Merck). Column chromatography was performed on silica gel. All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activities by broth dilution method.

Synthesis of 1-(4-[(4-chlorophenyl)methylene]amino)-phenyl)ethanone (1) : A mixture of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 M), 1-(4-aminophenyl)ethanone (0.01 M) and methanol (30 ml) was heated for about 5 min in a beaker (250 ml) to get a clear solution. The solution was kept overnight at room temperature to get the respective crude solid which was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the

Reaction Scheme

pure crystals of 1-(4-{{(4-chlorophenyl)methylene}amino}phenyl)ethanone respectively. The yield of the product was 75% and the product melts at 120 °C (Found : C, 69.88; H, 4.65; N, 5.41. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂ClNO : C, 69.91; H, 4.69; N, 5.43%).

Synthesis of 1-(4-acetylphenyl)-3-chloro-4-(4-chloro-

phenyl)azetidin-2-one (2) : In a 100 ml round bottom flask 1-(4-{{(4-chlorophenyl)methylene}amino}phenyl)ethanone (0.01 M) in 70 ml benzene was taken. To this chloro acetyl chloride (0.01 M) was added at room temperature with constant stirring followed by triethyl amine (1 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 7 h. After the completion of reaction, solvent was removed by vacuum distillation. The solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from toluene. The yield of the product was 60% and the product melts at 108 °C (Found : C, 61.07; H, 3.88; N, 4.17. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃Cl₂NO₂ : C, 61.10; H, 3.92; N, 4.19%).

Synthesis of 3-chloro-1-{4-[3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one (3) : To the solution of 1-(4-acetylphenyl)-3-chloro-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one (0.01 M) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 M) and 2% NaOH were added and refluxed for 10 h. After refluxing the reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled, filtered and neutralized with dil. HCl. The solid residue thus obtained was crystallized by absolute ethanol.

Synthesis of 3-chloro-1-{4-[5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-pyrazol-3-yl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one (4a-j) : A mixture of 3-chloro-1-{4-[3-(substituted phenyl)prop-2-enoyl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one (0.01 M) and 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.015 M) in ethanol (50 ml) refluxed gently for 3 h. Then the mixture was concentrated and allowed to cool. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from ethanol to give a pale brown solid; IR (4e), cm⁻¹ : 3041 (=C-H), 1728 (>C=O), 1643 (>C=N-), 1552 (>C=C<), 1452 (-CH₂, bend), 1313 (-C-N<), 1290 (-N-N), 663 (-C-Cl-), 3400 (>NH); ¹H NMR (4b) (DMSO, δ, ppm) : 3.62 (2H, d, CH₂- of pyrazol), 4.33 (1H, t, >CH-Ar of pyrazol), 4.80 (1H, d, >CH-Ar of azetidine), 5.32 (1H, d, >CH-Cl of azetidine), 6.56-7.92 (13H, m, Ar-H, -NH-), 9.64 (1H, s, Ar-OH).

Results and discussion.

Antimicrobial activity :

The MICs of synthesized compounds were carried out by broth micro dilution method as described by Rattan (2000). It is one of the non-automated *in vitro* bacterial susceptibility tests. This classic method yields a quantita-

Table 1. Antimicrobial activities 3-chloro-1-{4-[5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-pyrazol-3-yl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidin-2-one

Compd.	R	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity		
		Minimal inhibition concentration				Minimal inhibition concentration		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. clavatus</i>
4a	-2-Cl	100	150	125	100	1000	1000	800
4b	-2-OH	175	200	175	250	800	700	700
4c	-3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	225	225	150	200	> 1000	800	600
4d	-3-NO ₂	175	225	200	150	700	600	1000
4e	-4-Cl	100	175	100	175	700	> 1000	1000
4f	-4-N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	250	200	1250	200	500	1000	1000
4g	-4-OH	200	175	200	175	800	800	800
4h	-4-N(CH ₃) ₂	200	200	175	225	700	700	700
4i	CHO	175	225	200	125	750	600	800
4j	-2-OH- 3-OCH ₃	200	200	225	200	1000	800	> 1000

Table 2. Antibacterial activity : Minimal inhibition concentration
(The standard drugs)

Drug	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC 443	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> MTCC 1688	<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC 96	<i>S. pyogenus</i> MTCC 442
(Microgram/ml)				
Gentamycin	0.05	1	0.25	0.5
Ampicilin	100	-	250	100
Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50
Ciprofloxacin	25	25	50	50
Norfloxacin	10	10	10	10

Table 3. Antifungal activity : Minimal inhibition concentration
(The standard drugs)

Drug	<i>C. albicans</i> MTCC 227	<i>A. niger</i> MTCC 282	<i>A. clavatus</i> MTCC 1323
(Microgram/ml)			
Nystatin	100	100	100
Greseofulvin	500	100	100

tive result for the amount of antimicrobial agents that is needed to inhibit growth of specific microorganisms.

The *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of test compounds were assessed against 24 h cultures of several selected bacteria and fungi. The bacteria used were *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. pyogenus*. The fungi used were *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus*.

The antimicrobial activity was performed by broth dilution method in DMSO. Gentamycin, Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Ciprofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Nystatin and Greseofulvin were used as standard for the evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activities respectively.

The activity was reported by Minimal Inhibition Concentration. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Biological screening result of activities 3-chloro-1-{4-[5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-pyrazol-3-yl]phenyl}-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)azetidin-2-one based derivatives shows that compound (4a) have shown better activity against *E. coli* and *S. pyogenus*, while (4e) have shown better activity against *E. coli*, while rest of all compound possessed good activity against *S. aureus* in the range of 100–225 µg/ml. Compounds with substitution 2-chloro (4a), shown good antibacterial activity against *S. pyogenus*, while rest of all derivatives possessed good activity against *S. pyogenus* in the range of 125–250 µg/ml. Compound (4f) is found to be good antifungal activity against *C. albicans*, against standard drugs Greseofulvin. While rest of all derivatives are poor against *A. niger* and *A. clavatus*.

Conclusion :

The main focus of this research work was to synthesize, characterize and evaluate antimicrobial activities of

the newly synthesized pyrazoline derivatives, structures of synthesized compounds were confirmed and characterized with the help of analytical data's such as IR and ¹H NMR. In summary, we have described the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 3-chloro-1-{4-[5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-pyrazol-3-yl]phenyl}-4-(4-chlorophenyl)azetid-2-one. MIC values revealed that amongst newly synthesized compound having **4a**, **4e** and **4f** has shown good activity against the bacterial strains.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Principal and Management of Arts, Commerce & Science College, Borsad and Mansa for providing laboratory facilities, SAIF, Chandigarh for NMR spectra and Loyola Research Center – Xavier's College, Ahmedabad for IR spectra and Micro-care Laboratory, Surat, Gujarat, India for biological activity.

References

1. H. D. Hollis, J. L. Johnson, L. M. Werbel, W. R. Leopold, R. C. Jackson and E. F. Elslager, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1984, **27**, 253.
2. A. C. Grosscurt, R. Van Hes and K. Wellinga, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1979, **27**, 406.
3. V. M. Barot, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1996, **8**, 565.
4. S. S. Korgaokar, P. H. Patil, M. J. Shah and H. H. Parekh, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1996, **58**, 222.
5. E. Palaska, M. Aytemir, I. T. Uzbay and D. Erol, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **36**, 539.
6. P. Y. Rajendra, R. A. Lakshmana, L. Prasoona, K. Murali and K. P. Ravi, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2005, **15**, 5030.
7. Z. Ozdemir, H. B. Kandilici, B. Gumusel, U. Calis and A. A. Bilgin, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **42**, 373.
8. O. Ruhogluo, Z. Ozdemir, U. Calis, B. Gumusel and A. A. Bilgin, *Arzneimittel forschung*, 2005, **55**, 431.
9. R. H. Udipi, A. S. Kushnoor and A. R. Bhat, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1998, **8**, 63.
10. D. Nauduri and G. B. Reddy, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1998, **46**, 1254.
11. E. C. Taylor and H. H. Patel, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 8089.
12. H. Koga, A. Itoh, S. Murayama, S. Suzue and T. Irikura, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 1358.
13. J. A. Wilkinson, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 505.
14. R. Wise, J. M. Andrews and L. J. Edwards, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1983, **23**, 559.
15. S. E. Hagen, J. M. Domagala, C. L. Heifetz and J. Johnson, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 1155.
16. J. Matsumoto, T. Miyamoto, A. Minamada, Y. Mishimuna, H. Egawa and H. Nisimira, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1984, **27**, 292.
17. I. Hayakawa, T. Hiramitsu and Y. Tanaka, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Tokyo)*, 1984, **32**, 4907.